

Mediating Role of Green Training in Impact of Green Manufacturing on Performance in Apparel Industry

Sweta Jain^{1*}, Jacob Joseph Kalapurackal², Vedha Balaji³ & Sriram M⁴

School of Business and Management, Christ University, Bangalore, India

Abstract:

Background: *The garment export business makes a substantial contribution to both industrial production and export revenues. Implementing environmentally sustainable practices in the production process of garment export-oriented enterprises not only contributes to societal well-being but also enhances competitiveness in the global market and boosts overall company performance.*

Methods: *This study aims to investigate the impact of Green Manufacturing on Operational Performance, Environmental Performance, and Economic Performance in the apparel manufacturing export industry. Furthermore, the study investigates the role of Green Training as a mediator between Green Manufacturing and types of Performance. A survey method is used to collect data from 123 garment export units, and structural equation modelling (SEM) is used to analyze the results.*

Results: *This study delivers empirical evidence of the impact of the implementation of Green Manufacturing on Green Training, Operational Performance, Environmental Performance, and Economic Performance. The research provides empirical proof of the partial mediation of Green Training in the implementation of GM and its impact on Environmental Performances. Additionally, it demonstrates that Green Training has no significant mediation on Economic Performance and Operational Performance.*

Conclusion: *This study is unique as it empirically proves that businesses should include sustainability practices to maximize income through internal resources like green technology and trained manpower. This study suggests that implementing green practices can lead to improved firm operational, economic and environmental performance, which has practical implications for enterprises.*

Keywords: *garment, green manufacturing, green training, performance, sustainability*

*Corresponding Author:

Ms. Sweta Jain
Research Scholar,
School of Business and Management,
Christ University,
Hosur Road,
Bengaluru – 560 029
E-mail: sweta.jain@nift.ac.in

1. Introduction

The apparel market already uses more resources than the earth can sustain [1]. Over time, the garment industry has put more strain on the planet's resources, which has had a detrimental effect on society, the economy, and the environment [2]. India's export share is declining in the apparel, cotton fabric, and carpet sectors compared to Bangladesh, Vietnam, Turkey, and China [3]. According to Mariam [4], the stakeholders and policymakers participating in the recovery plan following Covid 19 should implement sustainable development goals. Businesses can get a competitive marketing edge by earning environmental management system (EMS) accreditations like LEED and WRAP [5]. The sustainability challenges associated with garment manufacturing must be addressed immediately due to the industry's reputation regarding it [6]. To lessen the industry's negative environmental effects, green manufacturing is one ecologically friendly approach that should be adopted.

2. Literature Review

Businesses use greener production methods to lessen the environmental impact of their products and production method [7].

According to Cay [8], adopting more eco-friendly production techniques is necessary for sustainable production. Businesses in the fashion industry that actively support green supply chains can better withstand export restrictions in international commerce and increase their competitiveness in the world market. Fashion firms are working to identify best practices based on economic, social, and environmental considerations

by incorporating sustainable strategies within the fashion supply chain and using eco-friendly materials, ethical labor practices, renewable energy, and green manufacturing [9]. A study investigates the impact of Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) practices on the performance of organizations operating in the garment sector of Sri Lanka [10]. Economic Performance is among the primary drivers behind the adoption of sustainable supply chain techniques. Green training is essential for green teams, claim [11]. Recent research explains how green training affects production plans with greener practices. Corporate training influences the creation of environmentally friendly supply chains.

Although there are several studies on green manufacturing and performance, none of them explicitly address the interrelationships within the apparel export industry. The relationship between green manufacturing, three categories of performance, and the mediating role of green training has not been investigated in the specific context of garment manufacturing export enterprises. In addition, quite a few previous research studies on green manufacturing were conceptual, qualitative, literature surveys, or investigations with other variables. As a result, studies based on quantitative data are still required [12]. International customers put more pressure on export-oriented organizations to adopt GMP [13], thus, the study focuses solely on export-oriented units in the garment industry. The research is unique because a gap exists, providing a valuable avenue for future research. It was assumed that green manufacturing is positively correlated to operational performance, environmental performance, and economic performance and that green training either has a direct or mediating effect.

2.1 Theory background

The framework known as the resource-based view (RBV) has been utilized to examine the importance of resources and their capabilities concerning product development and an organization's overall success. Furthermore, resource dependence theory examines the impact of green manufacturing practices on performance. Thus, theoretically speaking, green training is a talent that can be attained through resource utilization. The natural-resource-based approach (NRBV) was introduced by Hart [14] and highlights the skills that support the environment. To test the proposed conceptual research framework and research hypothesis, a survey was conducted in Indian apparel manufacturing companies. The study article is organized into various sections, with Section 3 describing the data collection and the methods utilized. Section 4 focuses on the results and discussion, and section 5 highlights the conclusion.

3. Method

3.1 Data Description

As discussed in the literature review, Green manufacturing has grown increasingly attractive and increased attention to environmental and sustainable development challenges in today's society. Additionally, Green Training considerably modified environmental practices in Spanish businesses, claims Sarkis [15]. Daily [11] asserts that green training is essential for green teams. We contend that green training and green manufacturing in the fashion industry continue to be significantly associated. Therefore, the interconnection between Green Manufacturing (GM) and Green Training (GT) is investigated with the hypothesis.

(H1): Green Manufacturing (GM) has a significant positive impact on Green Training (GT)

Furthermore, manufacturing companies accept sustainable and green production methods primarily to improve performance. A study investigates the impact of Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) practices on the performance of organizations operating in the garment sector of Sri Lanka [10]. Economic Performance is among the primary drivers behind the adoption of sustainable supply chain techniques. Therefore, based on the existing literature review, the study examines the connections between green manufacturing and three types of performance in the apparel manufacturing export industry: operational performance, environmental performance, and economic performance. The research hypotheses are as follows.

(H2): Green manufacturing has a significant impact on Economic Performance. (H3): Green manufacturing has a significant impact on Environmental Performance. (H4): Green manufacturing has a significant impact on Operational Performance.

Additionally, the study contends that green training plays an important mediating role between green manufacturing and three types of performance in the garment manufacturing export industry, adding to the pool of knowledge on green manufacturing. As a result, the following hypotheses is used to investigate the interconnections between the constructs:

(H5): Green Training has a significant mediating effect on Green manufacturing and Economic Performance. (H6): Green Training has a significant mediating effect on Green manufacturing and Environmental Performance. (H7): Green Training has a significant mediating effect on Green manufacturing and Operational Performance. (H8): Green Training has a significant impact on Economic Performance. (H9): Green Training has a significant impact on Environmental Performance. (H10): Green Training has a significant impact on Operational Performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

The conceptual research framework is presented by the literature review, and the research gap identified (see Figure 1). This exploratory study aims to discover the interconnections among the constructs of Green Manufacturing, Green Training, operational performance, environmental performance, and economic performance of Indian apparel manufacturing export companies. The research employs a deductive approach, quantitative analysis, and a questionnaire survey method for data collection. According to AEPC, there are 246 textile and apparel export companies in Karnataka, out of which 176 medium and large size and medium size apparel manufacturing units are identified as population, and the sample size is 123 [16].

3.2 Variable Measurement and Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire is divided into two sections: demographics and constructs. Five constructs are included in the study: Green Training, Green Manufacturing, and three performances. Shang et al. validated the Green Manufacturing construct, which included 15 items. Sarkis [15] and Daily [11] validated the Green Training construct, which had seven items. Hajmohammad [17] validated the construct of Environmental Performance (6 items), Zhu [18] validated Operational performance (5 items), and Zhu [19] validated Economic Performance (5 items).

The population for the study consists of export-oriented apparel manufacturing companies in the southern Indian state of Karnataka. EOU firm type and garment manufacturing industry type are used to determine the study population. The data is collected from garment manufacturing export houses using random sampling methods. The questionnaire developed was validated was academicians and industry people. The pilot study data analysis included 35 samples. After that constructs reliability, discriminant validity, and convergent validity were checked through preliminary examination of pilot test data. The final questionnaire was shared with the respondents to fill in the company's current GMP adoption status on a seven-point Likert scale. Respondents worked in various departments of the apparel manufacturing unit. For the electronic survey, 159 potential respondents were contacted, and 127 companies returned completed questionnaires. As a result, the return rate is 79.8%. The study used data from July to November 2023. Table 1 summarizes the demographics of the 123 respondents.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the companies

Job title	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Director	9	7.3	7.3
Manager	103	83.7	83.7
Product Developer	3	2.4	2.4
Vice president	8	6.5	6.5
Total	123	100.0	100.0
Age of the company	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
>=21	52	42.3	42.3

0-5 years	16	13.0	13.0
11-20 years	37	30.1	30.1
6-10 years	18	14.6	14.6
Total	123	100.0	100.0

3.3 Data Analysis Procedure

Given the widespread use of PLS-SEM in social science, marketing, and business strategy research, it is being implemented in this study for data analysis [20]. Moreover, it is common research practice to use structural equation modelling with PLS-SEM to demonstrate a theory using actual data [21].

Common Method Bias: It is a measurement source error that can result in inappropriate relationships between measurement items and, in the end, faulty study findings. Common Method Bias can be tested the Harman one-factor test from 1976. According to Podsakoff [22], the single construct's total variance is below the acceptable 50%. The research has a CMB of 42% and the VIF value is less than the recommended level of 3.4 [23]. As a result, the data is free of common method bias and collinearity.

Measurement Model: The validity and reliability of the constructs are evaluated using the measurement model [20] (See Table 2). Indicating that both Cronbach's alpha (CA) and Composite reliability (CR) are greater than the suggested 0.700, CA ranges from 0.881 to 0.956 and CR ranges from 0.907 to 0.957. As a result, all of the data used in the measurement model is reliable [21].

Table 2: Construct Reliability

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
EP	0.921	0.926	0.941	0.762
EnP	0.899	0.907	0.922	0.665
GM	0.956	0.957	0.959	0.684
GT	0.953	0.954	0.962	0.782
OP	0.881	0.913	0.911	0.672

Note(s): EP = Economic Performance, OP=Operational Performance, EnP = Environmental Performance, GT = Green Training

The average variance extracted (AVE) values, which range from 0.665 to 0.782 [24], are also used to verify the convergent validity of the constructs [21]. Cross-loading, the Fornell-Larcker criteria, and the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) are used to assess the discriminant validity. The square root of AVE is used in this work to test the Fornell-Larcker criteria, and its off-diagonal values are lower than the diagonal components [24] (see Table 3). The HTMT is less than 0.9 (see Table 4), indicating a satisfactory HTMT. As a result, constructs have required discriminant validity.

Table 3: Fornell–Larcker criterion

	EP	EnP	GM	GT	OP
EP	0.873				
EnP	0.387	0.815			
GM	0.765	0.543	0.833		
GT	0.574	0.676	0.726	0.884	
OP	0.284	0.574	0.410	0.421	0.820

Note(s): EP = Economic Performance, OP=Operational Performance, EnP = Environmental Performance, GT = Green Training

Table 4: Heterotrait–Monotrait ratio (HTMT)

	EP	EnP	GM	GT	OP
EP					
EnP	0.424				
GM	0.809	0.575			
GT	0.614	0.722	0.753		
OP	0.292	0.634	0.411	0.420	

Figure 2: Measurement model from smart PLS

Data analysis reveals the cross-loading matrix values are higher for intended constructs. The measurement model is shown in Figure 2, and it includes the development of a path diagram with constructs to evaluate the reliability, discriminant validity, and convergent validity of all six constructs used in the model.

4. Results and Discussion

Later, a structural equation model was created in smart PLS by bootstrapping with 10000 subsamples to assess statistical fit, check the significance of the impact of the constructs, and test all hypotheses identified during research. Then, the direct path coefficient value and the mediation effects between the construct are investigated. R2 value is determined [25], which measures the ability to explain the dependent variable, is good and significant for the structural equation model. Latan [25] states that the R2 value is less, if it is lower than 0.25, medium if it is lower than 0.50, and large if it is lower than 0.70.

Table 5. Path Coefficient

Hypothesis	CP	O	STDEV	TS	<i>p value</i>	Results
H1	GM -> GT	0.726	0.043	16.912	0.000	Supported
H4	GT -> EP	0.045	0.095	0.479	0.632	Not Supported
H2	GT -> EnP	0.585	0.077	7.610	0.000	Supported
H3	GT -> OP	0.261	0.131	1.997	0.046	Supported
H8	GM -> EP	0.766	0.043	17.632	0.000	Supported
H9	GM -> EnP	0.536	0.058	9.194	0.000	Supported
H10	GM -> OP	0.408	0.067	6.064	0.000	Supported

Note(s): CP= Construct Path, O = Original sample, STDEV = Standard deviation, TS = T statistics, PV= *p* Value

In the structural model, the R2 adjusted value accounts for 52.7% of the Green Training. The value of R2 adjusted for Economic Performance, Operational Performance and Environmental Performance is 58.6%, 20% and 46.3% respectively [20]. The P values, path coefficient (β), and t-statistics are used in the research study to assess the interconnections among the constructs. The relationship in H1, GM on GT ($t = 16.912$, $\beta = 0.726$, $p < 0.000$), successively for all other hypotheses is in Table 5. As a result, research hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H6, H8, H9, and H10 are supported, while H4, H5 and H7 is not. This signifies that except for Economic performance, Green training constructs directly and considerably impact the economic and operational Performance. Green Manufacturing constructs also directly and considerably impact green training, operational performance, environmental performance, and economic performance.

Table 6: Mediation table

H	Direct Effect Coff.	PV	Specific Indirect Effect	Indirect Coff.	PV	TE	LCL 2.5 %	UCL 97.5%	Mediation
H5	0.73	0.00	GM -> GT -> EP	0.03	0.64	0.77	-0.106	0.165	No mediation
H6	0.13	0.19	GM -> GT -> EnP	0.42	0.00	0.55	0.313	0.563	Partial mediation
H7	0.22	0.13	GM -> GT -> OP	0.19	0.05	0.41	-0.015	0.366	No mediation

Note(s): H = Hypothesis, CP= Construct Path, PV= *p* Value, TE = Total Effect

As shown by the test results of the Specific Indirect effect ($\beta = 0.033$, $p = 0.635$), there is no significant mediation of GT on GM and EP. There is partial positive significant mediation of GT on GM and EnP ($\beta = 0.424$, $p < 0.000$). Also, there is a no significant mediation of GT on GM as there is zero value in between LCL 2.5% and UCL 97.5%. Therefore, research hypotheses H5 and H7 have no mediation, and H6 have partial mediation.

Finally, the model fit is checked to understand the statistical adequacy of the structural model; the value of SRMR is close to .80, indicating that the research model is valid [25]. The values of LV predictive are mentioned in Table 8, where the predictive power of constructs is good and R^2 values are significant.

Table 7: LV predictive summary

	Q ² predict	R ²
EP	0.581	0.463
EnP	0.279	0.586
GT	0.522	0.527
OP	0.145	0.200

Note(s): RMSE = Root Mean Squared Error, MAE = Mean Absolute Error

Green training is thus significantly impacted by green manufacturing. This study signifies that except for Economic performance (PP), Green training construct directly and considerably impacts the economic and operational Performance. This research supports the literature, which emphasizes the importance of green training and its influence on the green economy. This study adds to current research on green manufacturing by showing a strong mediating influence of green training on green manufacturing and performance. The research provides further evidence to back up previous studies on the effects of Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) strategies on the productivity of companies in Sri Lanka's apparel industry [10].

4.1 Implications

Both academics and researchers will benefit from the study. Garment export companies competing for orders from other nations may utilize green training to adopt green manufacturing and plan business strategies to achieve organizational goals. The study's analysis of the mediating effects between the components significantly expands the pool of knowledge on green manufacturing. The research enables experts in the apparel sector to comprehend the significance of numerous concepts, such as green training and demands for green manufacturing implementation at the firm level, and to reset environmental resources appropriately. Finally, the research will assist garment exporters in growing their apparel export companies by getting certifications like LEED and ISO 14000 after applying green production.

4.2 Limitations

One of the study's limitations is that it was conducted in Karnataka's garment manufacturing export-oriented firms. The generalizability of study is constrained by the fact that the data is gathered from top or middle management at the firm level. There is an impact of knowledge of sustainable manufacturing practices on further studies in apparel [26], textiles [27] or textile technology [28]. Therefore, future studies may examine the moderating impact of constructs, including various business stakeholders in the textile and apparel industries.

5. Conclusion

The research provides empirical proof of the partial mediation of Green Training in the implementation of GM and its impact on environmental performances. Additionally, it demonstrates that Green Training has no significant mediation on Economic performance and Operational performance. Also, construct GM have a direct significant positive impact on OP, EnP and EP. Moreover, construct GT have a direct significant positive impact on OP and EnP. This supports the findings of other academics who hypothesize that the high upfront expenses associated with adopting sustainable practices could prevent them from having a beneficial short-term impact on profitability and sales. The garment export companies competing for orders from other nations may utilize green training to adopt green manufacturing and plan business strategies to achieve performance goals. Lastly, the study suggests that adopting green practices should be viewed as a long-term objective because it may not result in increased profitability or sales success.

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